

Assessment of Economic Benefits for EV Owners Participating in the Primary Frequency Regulation Markets

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Abstract — Transportation electrification plays an important role in developing more sustainable systems. As a result, the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) is increasingly endorsed by governmental policies. It can be even more encouraged by promoting the provision of different ancillary services using vehicle-to-grid (V2G) enabled EVs, since EV owners may obtain additional profit by market participation. This paper presents an assessment of the economic benefits of using EVs to participate in the primary frequency regulation markets from the EV owner perspective. A heuristic method is proposed to optimize the power bid that maximizes the EV owners' revenue along with a set of operational strategies that facilitates the service provision, which is evaluated using a simulation-based approach. A comparison analysis is performed to individually demonstrate the economic potential that four EVs with different battery capacities may offer to the owner when providing frequency-controlled normal operation reserves (FCR-N) in the Nord Pool market. The assessment of the power bid is performed considering the influence of the operation strategies and customer preferences. In addition, the effect of FCR-N on EV battery degradation and the grid impact caused by the service provision are considered in the economic evaluation. The results estimate annual benefits ranging between €100 and €1100 per vehicle, which demonstrates that EV owners can obtain substantial revenues by providing FCR-N.

Index Terms—Battery degradation, Economic assessment, Electric vehicles, Frequency regulation, Operation strategies, V2G services.

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This paper has not been presented at any conference and is not under review by another journal/conference.

This work was supported by the Brazilian institutions: Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES)-PSDE, process no. 88881.135226/2016-01 and the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP)- grant 2018/23617-7, Danish Parker project under ForskEL contract no. 2016-1-12410, and Danish BOSS project under EUDP contract no. 64018-0618.

NOMENCLATURE

A. Parameters and variables

CL^{DoD}	Number of cycles in terms of the depth of discharge (DoD)
\bar{E}	Maximum capacity of the battery
\underline{E}	Minimum energy required by the EV owner
f	Frequency measurements
f^{hist}	Set of historical frequency measurements
f^{min}, f^{max}	Minimum and maximum frequency deviations
p^{bid}	Power bid
p^{cong}	Total power causing congestion
p^{max}	Maximum rated power
p^{prov}	Power provided
p^{req}	Power requested
\bar{p}^g	Maximum power consumption from the grid
$\underline{p}^{max}, \bar{p}^{max}$	Minimum and maximum value of the rated power
SOC_s	Current state of charge (SOC) at time s
SOC^{ini}	Initial SOC
SOC^{obj}	Predefined SOC set by the customer
$\underline{SOC}, \overline{SOC}$	Minimum and maximum SOC of the battery
$\underline{SOC}^{OF}, \overline{SOC}^{OF}$	Minimum and maximum SOC allowed in the over-fulfillment strategy
$\underline{SOC}^{POP}, \overline{SOC}^{POP}$	Minimum and maximum SOC allowed in the POP strategy
β^{DoD}	Number of cycles performed by the battery at a specific DoD
$\bar{\beta}$	Capacity fade of the battery
Γ	Non-analytical function
δ	Total battery degradation
δ^{DoD}	Battery degradation for each DoD
δ^{sprov}	Battery degradation caused by the service provision
δ^{transp}	Battery degradation caused by daily travel requirements
Δ_s	Granularity of the contracted regulation period
Δ^{DoD}	Discretization of the cycle life curve
Δp^{max}	Discrete steps of the rated power
Υ	Expected years of usable capacity of the battery
$\bar{\Upsilon}$	Rated battery life
η^c	Charger efficiency
λ	Number of hours during the contracted regulation period
λ^{da}	Daily availability factor of the EV
μ^{fs}	Utilization factor of the power capacity bid
Π	Contracted regulation period
σ	Percentage of over-fulfillment
ζ^c	Power capacity price
ζ^e	Energy cost
ζ^b	Battery replacement cost
τ	Non-fulfillment of the service or unavailability
\bar{T}	Maximum permitted time of non-fulfillment of the service
φ	Total time exceeding \bar{p}^g during Π
$\bar{\varphi}$	Maximum congestion time
Ωp^{bid}	Set of possible values for the power bid

I. INTRODUCTION

TRANSPORTATION electrification has gained momentum in recent years. Various countries are adopting electric vehicles (EVs) supported by multi-government policies as a way to move toward more sustainable systems [1]. As a result, it is foreseen that EVs will be integrated quickly into the electric power system, which may bring several opportunities for different stakeholders. Besides being an environmentally friendly option, EVs have the advantage that they can also bring economic benefits to the owners. EVs carry lower running and maintenance costs than conventional vehicles [2]. Moreover, considering that EVs are purchased for the primary purpose of transportation, EV owners can gain additional revenues by providing services to power systems when the car is not being used for its primary purpose.

Vehicle-to-grid (V2G) enabled EVs are able to support power systems by providing different ancillary services (e.g., operational reserves such as frequency regulation, spinning and non-spinning reserves and supplemental reserves), maintaining a balance between supply and demand in a short-term planning horizon (i.e., daily or hourly) [3]–[6], decreasing the peak load [7], or reducing losses [8]. For instance, primary reserve or primary frequency regulation (PFR) is a service procured by transmission system operators (TSOs) to ensure the balance between generation and consumption. V2G-enabled EVs are a prominent option to provide this service due to their fast response time as well as low energy commitments and well-remunerated payments [9], [10]. Currently, V2G is still an on-development technology that still faces many barriers for its implementation in real-life applications. However, there is a notable interest in adopting this technology in the future EV market, supported by many R&D projects regarding V2G technologies [11]. Demonstrating that EVs are capable to provide services to the power system and that EV owners may obtain additional revenues for the provision of services is a way to encourage first, the EV industry to produce EVs compatible with V2G technologies; and second, the use of more EVs, since besides producing additional revenues, they are a “green” option for transportation that helps to achieve environmental targets. Hence, it becomes significant to assess the attainable economic benefit for EV owners from participating in PFR markets.

The economic benefit of providing PFR depends on several aspects, such as the payment schemes, market structure, operation strategy, degradation cost, unavailability fines and penalties caused by increasing the peak load triggering technical issues on the distribution grid. For this reason, the economic benefit for individual EV owners may vary from country to country. Most of the previous studies assess the benefit of EVs participating in North American PFR markets, but few studies have addressed this topic in the European systems. According to a recent study, frequency containment and restoration reserve may be the most feasible service for EVs in the European region [12]. Additionally, a great number of studies have dedicated to design and model the operation of EV aggregators to provide V2G regulation services, aiming at maximizing the aggregators’ revenue [13]–[17]; however, few works have dedicated to analyzing the economic benefit of providing PFR from the EV owner perspective. Furthermore, despite that, there is a notable interest in promoting V2G applications in the Nordic area [18]–[22], the capability

and economic potential of individual EVs with different characteristics participating in PFR markets, especially in this area have not been thoroughly investigated. For instance, in [19] and [22], the economic value of a specific EV brand (Nissan Leaf) providing reserve in Nordic countries is quantified through a stochastic optimization model and an analytical method, but disregarding possible penalties for service unavailability and grid impact within the optimization. The authors in [23] are among the first describing the operation of a group of EVs participating in North American PFR markets and calculating the expected incomes of each EV. In [24], a cost-benefit analysis of EVs providing PFR is presented. The analysis includes the limitations of the service provision, and the power bid is calculated to satisfy the user requirements. In [25], an economic analysis of EVs providing different services in the UK is provided, considering the costs associated with the deployment of V2G infrastructures. In [26], the expected revenue of an EV owner from providing unidirectional and V2G services is presented; analytical methods are used to estimate the power capacity of an EV fleet exploring regulation strategies for both unidirectional and V2G services in [27]–[34], and [35] considers investment, operating and infrastructure costs in the economic analysis for EV fleets. In [13] and [16], a decision-making model and a simulation approach are proposed to manage the charging/discharging actions of an EV fleet providing PFR and to validate the economic feasibility of providing this service.

Most of the previous works have been dedicated to estimating the power bid that maximizes the revenue from the aggregator point of view, and the EV owner preferences—as well as the potential costs for EV owners—are neglected. For instance, the battery degradation cost caused by providing PFR services is usually disregarded in the bid calculations, which may affect the benefit calculation [36]. Despite that [13] and [16] consider battery degradation costs within the economic calculations, the benefit is calculated in an aggregated mode from the aggregator's perspective. Furthermore, the battery degradation is considered as a cost function that depends on the total energy discharged and the energy charged using fast chargers, without specifically considering the degradation curve. In addition, the costs associated with the impact of PFR on the local grid as well as the potential fines resulting from the unavailability of service are usually neglected in the optimization problem. Moreover, suitable strategies to decrease service unavailability or increase battery lifespan are not presented in detail, and their effects on the power bid are not discussed.

In this paper, a method is proposed to optimize the power bid that maximizes the benefit of EV owners by providing frequency-controlled normal operation reserve (FCR-N), which is the primary frequency reserve in the Nord Pool market. The proposed method works based on a local search algorithm that carries out an exhaustive search of the power bid that maximizes the EV owners' revenue. The contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows. Different from the previous cost-benefit analysis, the economic assessment in this paper address the revenue from the EV owner's perspective. The algorithm is individually executed for each EV in order to analyze the behavior and the economic potential that each EV may offer to the owner when providing FCR-N, according to their characteristics. In contrast to previous works in which the operation strategies to provide PFR remain in

theoretical applications, this paper proposes three simple and practical strategies, one of them being practically tested in real-world implementation of V2G through the Parker project. Parker is the first project in the Nordic area demonstrating FCR-N using cross-brand EVs [37]. The operation strategies help to reduce potential costs due to unavailability of service, grid impact, and battery degradation. Moreover, the annual benefit for an EV owner providing FCR-N is estimated through a one-year simulation using realistic frequency data. It allows the method to account for the nature of this unpredictable and fast fluctuating variable and to provide more accurate results. The comparison analysis is performed using four different EVs used in the Parker project [38].

This paper is organized as follows. Section II presents an overview of PFR services and describes the operation strategies for EVs participating in the PFR markets. Section III describes the problem formulation and the proposed method to assess the economic benefit for EVs providing FCR-N. The simulations and results are presented in Section IV. Finally, discussions and conclusions are provided in Section V and VI.

II. FREQUENCY REGULATION

Frequency regulation is one of the most common ancillary services procured by TSOs who are responsible for grid stability. The main target of frequency regulation is to maintain the balance between electricity consumption and production to provide a high-quality power service. In case of over-production, the frequency increases, and down-regulation is required. Contrarily, in case of over-consumption, the frequency decreases, and up-regulation is required. Thus, frequency regulation deals with frequency deviations by containing and restoring the frequency to its nominal value. Power plants and generator units have traditionally provided this service. Currently, other sources such as renewable energy units, energy storage systems (e.g., stationary batteries (BES) and EVs) are being used to provide PFR (through pilot demonstrations for the case of EVs). To participate in the frequency regulation market, EVs act as production or consumption units, charging or discharging their batteries according to the frequency signal. Thus, when upward regulation (negative) is required, the car should discharge the battery, while in downward regulation (positive) the battery should be charged.

Frequency regulation can be divided into three types: Primary, secondary and tertiary. They differ in terms of the activation control, time response, droop control and power requirements. Moreover, the name, the operational conditions, and the economic benefit of each kind of regulation service may vary from country to country and according to the market characteristics [10]. PFR in particular may be the most interesting service for BES and EVs in Europe, especially for V2G enabled EVs due to their characteristics, i.e., time used for mobility, initial investments, quick response time, low energy and power requirements, and the payment structure and compensation for the service [9], [10]. This paper will focus on calculating the benefit that an EV owner may obtain from providing primary frequency regulation. The benefit is calculated individually (per vehicle), using four different brands of EVs. It is worth mentioning that the operation strategies are proposed to optimize the power bid, not to validate their

impact on the grid frequency improvement, as the operation of one individual EV would not provoke significant effects on the grid frequency improvement.

A. Primary Frequency Regulation around Europe

The regulations associated with the PFR differ for each regional group. In most cases, the power is supplied linearly according to a droop defined in terms of the power bid and the nominal, minimum and maximum frequency deviations. In Germany, France, Spain, Belgium and Denmark-DK1, power is supplied linearly for frequency deviations of $\pm 200\text{mHz}$. However, there is a small dead-band allowed for frequency deviations of $\pm 10\text{mHz}$ (Germany) and $\pm 20\text{mHz}$ (France and DK1) in which the service provision is not mandatory. In the UK and Poland, the frequency deviation allowed is $\pm 500\text{mHz}$. In some markets, such as in Denmark-DK2, located in Region Nordic, the dead-band is not allowed. A summary of PFR market regulations and characteristics in countries belonging to the European Union can be found in [12], [39]. In terms of the offers, Germany, UK, and Denmark only accept symmetric offers for some PFR services, while France and Poland allow non-symmetric or separated offers.

Denmark is split into two synchronous areas: Jutland and Funen belong to Regional Group (RG) continental Europe, and Zealand belongs to RG Nordic. These areas are termed Western Denmark or DK1 and Eastern Denmark or DK2, respectively. In DK1, the primary frequency reserve and secondary reserves are available, while in DK2, two PFR can be found: frequency-controlled normal operation reserve (FCR-N) and frequency-controlled disturbance reserve (FCR-D). This paper focuses on the economic benefits for EV owners participating in the FCR-N market. It is estimated through a one-year simulation using realistic frequency data, which behavior during some periods of the year is depicted in Fig. 1a. Further frequency analysis is presented in [40].

For FCR-N, the frequency deviation allowed is $\pm 100\text{mHz}$ without any permitted dead-band. The power activation is given by the general droop control represented by (1). Thus, the power requested (P^{req}) depends on the power bid (P^{bid}), the frequency measurements (f), and the minimum and the maximum frequency deviations (f^{min} and f^{max} , equal to 49.9Hz and 50.1Hz, respectively). More details regarding the characteristics of the PFR services available in Denmark can be found in [41].

$$P^{req} = \begin{cases} P^{bid}, & \text{if } f > f^{max} \\ \frac{2P^{bid} \cdot (f - f^{min})}{(f^{max} - f^{min})} - P^{bid}, & \text{if } f^{min} \leq f \leq f^{max} \\ -P^{bid}, & \text{if } f < f^{min} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The frequency signal defines the P^{req} according to the droop control described in (1) and the EV should respond to it by providing the requested power, i.e., P^{prov} . In some cases, the EV may not be able to provide P^{req} , as the EV may be fully charged or discharged. In those cases, P^{prov} is equal to zero.

Fig. 1a). Frequency fluctuation during representative months of each season in a year.

Fig. 1b). Flowchart of the PFR algorithm.

The state of charge (SOC) of the battery must be updated according to (2) and (3), considering the minimum and maximum limits as defined in (4).

$$SOC_s = SOC_{s-1} + \frac{P_s^{prov} \cdot \eta^c \cdot \Delta_s}{\bar{E}}, \text{ if } P_s^{req} > 0 \quad (2)$$

$$SOC_s = SOC_{s-1} + \frac{P_s^{prov} \cdot \Delta_s}{\eta^c \cdot \bar{E}}, \text{ if } P_s^{req} < 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\underline{SOC} \leq SOC_s \leq \overline{SOC} \quad (4)$$

Where \overline{SOC} is the maximum SOC of the battery, SOC_s is the current SOC at time s , η^c is the charger efficiency, \bar{E} is the maximum capacity of the battery and Δ_s is the granularity of the contracted regulation period (Π). The PFR algorithm is described in Fig. 1b).

B. Operation Strategies for EVs Providing PFR

According to the previous framework, it is expected that the battery reaches its maximum or minimum capacity (i.e., fully charged or fully discharged) at some point. This may hinder the fulfillment of the service and may cause higher battery degradation. To deal with those problems and thus maximize the benefit of providing PFR, three operation strategies are proposed: complete pauses, over-fulfillment, and a preferred operating point mechanism, which are developed to be applied in the real-time operation. The main purpose of these strategies is to keep the battery within the operational range when providing services and to determine the most profitable way to operate the EV in terms of availability and the battery lifespan. Consequently, the value of P^{prov} in Fig.1 is modified according to the rules of each operation strategy described below.

1) Complete Pause (CP)

This strategy is the most simple, and consists of allowing predefined time periods to restore the SOC when the battery is reaching its minimum or maximum limits due to service provision. It may happen when the battery is fully charged or discharged. In those cases, a pause is activated and the EV is no longer able to provide service, i.e., P^{prov} is equal to zero. During the pause, the SOC is recovered to a predefined SOC (SOC^{obj}) that can be set by the customer. The complete pause is flexible, e.g., it can be defined as the total time required to reach the SOC^{obj} . In case of a pause, the SOC will be restored by charging or discharging the battery at the maximum rated power as shown in (5). For this case, the SOC is updated using (6) and (7).

$$P^{char} = \begin{cases} P^{\max}, & \text{if } SOC < SOC^{obj} \\ -P^{\max}, & \text{if } SOC > SOC^{obj} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$SOC_s = SOC_{s-1} + \frac{P_s^{char} \cdot \eta^c \cdot \Delta_s}{E}, \text{ if } SOC_s < SOC^{obj} \quad (6)$$

$$SOC_s = SOC_{s-1} + \frac{P_s^{char} \cdot \Delta_s}{\eta^c \cdot E}, \text{ if } SOC_s > SOC^{obj} \quad (7)$$

2) Over-fulfillment (OF)

This strategy consists of allowing modifications of P^{req} in a predefined percentage σ according to the policy described in (8). In case the SOC is less than the minimum allowed (\underline{SOC}^{OF}) and down-regulation is requested, the EV will be charged more than P^{req} according to (8). In case the SOC is higher than the maximum allowed (\overline{SOC}^{OF}) and up-regulation is requested, the EV will be discharged more than P^{req} according to (8). Moreover, when the battery is fully charged or discharged, the SOC is recovered as in the complete pause strategy described in section II-B.1).

$$P^{prov} = \begin{cases} P^{req} + \sigma \cdot P^{req}, \text{ if } SOC \leq \underline{SOC}^{OF} \text{ and } P^{req} > 0 \\ P^{req} + \sigma \cdot P^{req}, \text{ if } SOC \geq \overline{SOC}^{OF} \text{ and } P^{req} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

3) Preferred Operating Point (POP)

The POP is a mechanism used to ensure a suitable EV's SOC and to be able to provide services at any time. The strategy consists of defining a set point at which the EV will charge or discharge its battery based on the frequency signal with a flexible operating point. The POP can be calculated using different policies, and it should be activated within short intervals. In this paper, a droop control is proposed to calculate the POP based on a specific minimum and maximum SOC as shown in (9). Finally, (10) defines the power provided within this strategy.

$$POP = \begin{cases} \frac{-P^{max}}{(SOC^{POP})} \cdot (SOC - \underline{SOC}^{POP}), & \text{if } SOC < \underline{SOC}^{POP} \\ \frac{P^{max}}{(1 - \overline{SOC}^{POP})} \cdot (SOC - \overline{SOC}^{POP}), & \text{if } SOC > \overline{SOC}^{POP} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$P^{prov} = P^{req} + POP \quad (10)$$

The power provided is always limited by the maximum power of the charger as shown in (11), and the SOC of the battery should be always updated using (2)–(4) or (6)–(7) according to the implemented operation strategy. Note that in (11), the absolute value of P^{prov} is considered since it can be negative or positive (up or down-regulation, respectively) in line with the convention previously defined.

$$|P^{prov}| \leq P^{max} \quad (11)$$

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION AND OPTIMIZATION PROCESS

The economic benefit for EV owners participating in PFR markets depends on several parameters. In this formulation, the benefit is calculated by considering the incomes (12) and the costs (13) of participating in PFR markets. The incomes are calculated by a capacity payment (I^{CP}) and the energy exchanged (I^{EE}). The costs are calculated by a penalty for the unavailability time (C^{UP}), a penalty for causing congestion problems on the grid (C^{GI}), and the battery degradation cost (C^{BD}). All of them are calculated for a contracted regulation period (Π); for example, one year.

$$Income = I^{CP} + I^{EE} \quad (12)$$

$$Cost = C^{UP} + C^{GI} + C^{BD} \quad (13)$$

A. Incomes

As described in (12), the income from providing FCR-N in particular is calculated by using a capacity payment scheme based on the power capacity of the EV (P^{bid}), the corresponding number of hours (λ) during Π , and the power capacity price (ζ^c), as described in (14). I^{CP} can be adapted to any payment structure according to the contracted service. This scheme allows the EV

owner to generate incomes regardless of usage. Moreover, total energy is exchanged between the power grid and the EV owner during Π . Thus, I^{EE} is calculated based on P^{bid} , λ , and a utilization factor of the power capacity bid when providing up-regulation (μ^{fs}) with its corresponding energy price (ζ^e), as shown in (15) and (16).

$$I^{CP} = P^{bid} \cdot \lambda \cdot \zeta^c \quad (14)$$

$$I^{EE} = P^{bid} \cdot \mu^{fs} \cdot \lambda \cdot \zeta^e \quad (15)$$

$$\mu^{fs} = P^{req} / P^{bid} \quad (16)$$

B. Unavailability penalties

The benefit of an EV owner providing PFR may be jeopardized by the non-fulfillment of the service. In that case, the payment is reduced proportionally to Π and the EV owner may be quarantined or even precluded from providing services in future cases. In this formulation, the non-fulfillment of the service or unavailability (τ) is defined as the total time of non-availability and/or delivery of a non-conforming service during Π , as shown in (17). Thus, each time the TSO sends a signal of the power that is required (P^{req}) according to the droop control defined in (1) and the EV is not available (i.e., it is fully charged or discharged), as shown in (18), it is counted as an unavailability time.

$$\tau = \sum_{s=1}^{\Pi} \tau_s \quad (17)$$

$$\tau_s = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } 0 < SOC_s < 1 \\ 1, & \text{if } SOC_s = 1 \text{ or } SOC_s = 0 \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

Considering the possibility that the TSO allows short periods of non-fulfillment, constraint (19) is proposed to include a maximum permitted time of non-fulfillment (\bar{T}) and a penalization cost for exceeding this value. In this way, the EV owner has a level of flexibility in case unexpected/unforeseen issues arise during Π .

$$C^{UP} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \tau < \bar{T} \\ 2I^{CP} & \text{if } \tau \geq \bar{T} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

C. Grid impact penalty

An additional issue that arises when providing PFR is the impact on the distribution grid. This consideration arises because the EVs are mainly connected to distribution networks, and EV charging actions may cause congestion in the grid. Thus, a penalty cost is included in the formulation in an attempt to avoid congestion issues. Considering a maximum power consumption from the grid (\bar{P}^g) to avoid congestion [42], the total time exceeding \bar{P}^g during Π (i.e., φ) is calculated using (20)–(22).

$$P_s^{prov} = P^{bid} \cdot \mu_s^{fs} \quad (20)$$

$$\varphi_s = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } P_s^{prov} < \bar{P}^g \\ 1, & \text{if } P_s^{prov} \geq \bar{P}^g \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

$$\varphi = \sum_{s=1}^{\Pi} \varphi_s \quad (22)$$

Considering a flexibility level from the distribution operator in terms of the time causing congestion problems, a maximum congestion time ($\bar{\varphi}$) is included. Finally, the penalty for the grid impact is calculated in proportion to the total time (in hours), the total power causing congestion (φ and P^{cong} , respectively), and the energy cost (ζ^e), as described in (23) and (24).

$$P^{cong} = \sum_{s=1}^{\Pi} P_s^{prov} \cdot \varphi_s \quad (23)$$

$$C^{Gl} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \varphi < \bar{\varphi} \\ \zeta^e \cdot P^{cong} / 3600 & \text{if } \varphi \geq \bar{\varphi} \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

D. Battery degradation cost

Battery degradation may be a limitation when maximizing the benefit from the participation in PFR markets [36]. Assessing the battery degradation that is caused by providing PFR is still challenging, and the lack of information regarding this aspect from the battery manufacturing companies is one of the main issues. On the other hand, part of battery degradation is also caused by using the EVs for transportation as discussed in [43]. Therefore, the total battery degradation (δ) is resulted from both daily travel requirements (δ^{transp}) and the service provision (δ^{sprov}) as shown in (25). In this paper only battery degradation from the service provision part is considered, however, battery degradation due to daily travel requirements could be separately calculated as presented in [43], and easily joined to the calculation of the total battery degradation.

$$\delta = \delta^{transp} + \delta^{sprov} \quad (25)$$

Different methods have been proposed to estimate battery degradation [44],[45],[46]. Battery degradation depends on the battery technology, temperature, SOC, depth of discharge (DoD) and charging and discharging current, all of which are directly affected by P^{bid} . In this paper, the battery degradation caused by the services provision (δ^{sprov}) is estimated by using the battery cycle life method proposed in [24]. This method uses a semi-logarithmic function to calculate the number of cycles in terms of the DoD (CL^{DoD}) at 80% of the battery's end of life (EoL). As this function provides the battery cycle life for a specific DoD, then it is necessary to calculate the number of cycles that the battery performs at a specific DoD (β^{DoD}) during Π . β^{DoD} depends on the SOC pattern after the regulation period, and it is calculated using the rainflow-counting algorithm [47], [48], as used in [45]. The cycle life curve provided in [24] is discretized in intervals Δ^{DoD} by considering the maximum DoD as 100%. The total number of

DoD intervals (TID) is calculated using (26) and the battery degradation for each DoD interval (δ^{DoD}) is calculated according to β^{DoD} , the function CL^{DoD} proposed in [24] and its corresponding capacity fade $\bar{\beta}$, as shown in (27). Finally, δ is calculated using (28).

$$TID = \frac{100\%}{\Delta^{DoD}} \quad (26)$$

$$\delta^{DoD} = \beta^{DoD} \cdot \bar{\beta} / CL^{DoD} \quad (27)$$

$$\delta^{sprov} = \sum_{DoD=1}^{TID} \delta^{DoD} \quad (28)$$

After estimating δ , it is possible to calculate the battery life expectancy i.e., the expected years of usable capacity (Υ), assuming a rated battery life ($\bar{\Upsilon}$) and its corresponding $\bar{\beta}$, as shown in (29). Thus, given a battery replacement cost (ζ^b) in €/kWh per year, C^{BD} is calculated as a function of Υ and in proportion to the difference between the rated and the battery life expectancy, as shown in (30). Additionally,

$$\Upsilon = \bar{\beta} / \delta \quad (29)$$

$$C^{BD} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \Upsilon > \bar{\Upsilon} \\ \frac{\bar{E} \cdot \zeta^b}{\bar{\Upsilon}} \cdot (\bar{\Upsilon} - \Upsilon), & \text{if } \Upsilon \leq \bar{\Upsilon} \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

In the previous formulation, each term comprising the benefit of the EV owner is affected by the decision variable P^{bid} . P^{bid} may influence the incomes and the costs that result in a conflictive decision for the user. For instance, the higher P^{bid} is, the higher incomes are expected to be because of the capacity payment. However, a high value of P^{bid} may result in a high unavailability time or in a higher battery degradation due to the amount of power that is injected or extracted and the corresponding number of cycles. It means that the decision-making process is not trivial. Hence, the problem consists of finding an optimized bid for each EV that maximizes the economic benefit for an EV owner participating in the PFR market, as described in (31). Thus, the only variable that is intended to be optimized is P^{bid} . The optimal solution will be the P^{bid} that produces greater revenues for each EV owner according to each EV brand. Finding the optimal P^{bid} is very difficult since the problem is highly complex and hard to solve through classical optimization techniques. Moreover, the frequency signals are highly variable and unpredictable, and they are not known *a priori*. For this reason, we propose a heuristic-based optimization process to find an optimized power bid based on local search algorithms, which are usually employed to solve highly complex optimization problems [49], [50].

Fig. 2. Framework of the proposed optimization method.

$$\max_{p^{bid}} \mathbf{Benefit} = (\text{Income} - \text{Cost})$$

s.t.

$$0 \leq P^{bid} \leq P^{max}$$

(1) – (4),

(5) – (7), if operation strategy = CP

(8), if operation strategy = OF

(9) – (10), if operation strategy = POP

(11) – (30)

(31)

E. Optimization process

The proposed method estimates the P^{bid} that should be offered to maximize the benefit of an EV owner participating in PFR markets. A simulation-based approach is used to evaluate the operation of each EV within the three operation strategies. Considering a non-analytical function Γ and a set of input parameters as shown in (32), Γ returns the necessary variables to calculate the benefit as the optimization problem (1) – (30) is embedded in this function. Γ is a computational procedure that executes the operation of the EV for every regulation signal (provided by the TSO with a resolution of one second).

$$\Gamma(f^{hist}, P^{max}, \bar{E}, \underline{E}, SOC^{ini}) = \mu^{fs}, \tau, \varphi, \delta \quad (32)$$

Figure 2 shows the framework of the proposed method to solve the optimization problem (31). The inputs are represented by the market conditions (e.g., droop control, minimum offer, frequency signal, etc.), battery capacity, usable capacity, initial SOC, charger capacity, and the operation strategy to be used within the simulations. As a result, the main variables of the problem associated with the incomes and the cost are obtained.

In (32), f^{hist} is a set of historical frequency measurements, P^{max} is the charger capacity, \bar{E} is the battery capacity, and \underline{E} is the minimum energy required by the EV owner at any time and SOC^{ini} is the initial SOC. A set of possible values for P^{bid} is created by considering that P^{bid} is the variable to be optimized and that it is constrained by P^{max} . P^{bid} is discretized by using a minimum

and maximum value (i.e., \underline{P}^{max} and \bar{P}^{max} , respectively), and an additional parameter that represents discrete steps, (i.e., ΔP^{max}). Those parameters are defined *a priori* according to the technical conditions given by the inputs. As a result, a set of possible power bids is obtained, as shown in (33), and the simulations are executed for each $P^{*bid} \in \Omega P^{bid}$.

$$\Omega P^{bid} = \left\{ \underline{P}^{max}, \underline{P}^{max} + \Delta P^{max}, \dots, \bar{P}^{max} \right\} \quad (33)$$

In this case, it is worth mentioning that FCR-N is used to validate the proposed method. However, it could be applied to any PFR market by simply adapting the power control droop to the specific market conditions of the service.

IV. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

In this section, the proposed method will be adapted to optimize the power bid and the benefit of EV owners providing services in the context of the PFR market in Denmark.

A. Simulation Assumptions

The simulation results will gather the annual benefit that an EV owner may obtain by providing FCR-N. For this purpose, the simulations are executed for one complete year (i.e., the total contracted regulation period (Π) is equal to one year and λ is equal to 8640 hours) by using historical data for frequency with one second resolution (Δ_s), as well as average 2017 prices for the availability payment and the electricity price, 23.23 €/MWh/h and 31.95 €/MWh, respectively [51]. The grid impact cost is considered only for downward regulation cases, since in those cases the EV should consume power from the grid (charge the battery). It provokes a demand increase, for which congestions or overloading in components are likely to happen. The maximum power consumption (\bar{P}^g) per user is set as 7kW [42]. \bar{T} and $\bar{\varphi}$ are defined as 1% and 5%, respectively. For the battery degradation calculations, 3000 cycles at 100% DoD are considered [24], $\bar{\beta}$ is equal to 20%, \bar{Y} is equal to 10 years and the replacement cost is defined as 158 €/kWh according to [52], [53].

The simulations are performed by using four EV brands (with different technical characteristics, such as range of miles, performance, charge port, energy consumption, dimensions, and weight) as part of the EV fleet used in the Parker project [38]. A Mitsubishi Outlander PHEV, a Peugeot iOn, a Nissan e-NV200 Evalia, and a Nissan Leaf with maximum battery capacities (\bar{E}) of 12, 16, 24 and 30kWh, respectively, compose it. The minimum energy required by the EV owner (\underline{E}) is 30% of the maximum battery capacity. Furthermore, an Enel V2G charger with maximum capacity (P^{max}) of 10kW is used assuming a unitary charger efficiency (η^c). Then, the maximum bid is defined as ± 10 kW, considering the symmetric condition. Moreover, ΔP^{max} is equal to 1kW, \underline{P}^{max} and \bar{P}^{max} are 0 kW and 10 kW, respectively, and the minimum bid condition is disregarded.

The simulations are performed considering a base-case scenario (S-BC) in which there is no operation strategy (the battery will charge or discharge only according to the frequency signal). The other scenarios correspond to each operation strategy that is described in Section II. In the CP strategy, pauses of 30 minutes are allowed. Furthermore, the OF strategy is activated when the SOC of the EV is below 40% (\underline{SOC}^{OF}) and above 80% (\overline{SOC}^{OF}) and the percentage of over-fulfillment (σ) is settled as 20%. The POP is allowed to change in time intervals of 15 minutes and is activated when the SOC is below 30% (\underline{SOC}^{POP}) or above 70% (\overline{SOC}^{POP}). Moreover, SOC^{obj} is equal to 50%; and \underline{SOC} and \overline{SOC} are equal to 30% and 100%, respectively. The simulations and analysis performed in this study were carried out considering the steady-state operation of the EV battery and charger, as well as power systems, in which the EV battery is modeled as a constant active power load when charging and a constant power generator when discharging, and the charger only considers the charging/discharging efficiency.

The annual benefit that an EV owner may obtain from providing FCR-N is assessed by considering two case studies. In Case A, customer preferences are disregarded, and the EVs act as stationary batteries that are always available to provide the service. Thus, it is supposed that the EV is connected to the grid for the whole year. In Case B, assuming that the EV owner wishes to keep a minimum range to cover the daily commutes or emergency trips, the usable capacity is reduced by 30%. This percentage is selected by considering the average travel distance per day in Denmark [54]. Moreover, the daily operation of the EV (which includes arrival/departure time, trips duration, and travelling frequency) is considered through a daily availability factor of the EV (λ^{da}), based on the results provided in [55]. In [55], it is estimated with a 99% of confidence level that an EV is available to provide services around 13h per day. In this context, λ^{da} , which represents the percentage of time in which the EV is available to provide services per day is used to define the total contracted regulation period (given by $\Pi \cdot \lambda^{da}$). Thus, for Case A, λ^{da} is equal to one and Π remains equal to one year, while for Case B, λ^{da} is equal to 0.54 approximately, resulting in a decrease of Π . This case is proposed to assess the impact of the customer preferences on the P^{bid} and on the benefit. The proposed method is implemented and solved using Matlab.

B. Results

The annual benefits that an EV owner may obtain from providing FCR-N when considering Cases A and B are shown in Tables I and II, respectively (feasible solutions are remarked in bold font, the best solution is the one with the highest value). The results are shown for each EV brand and each operation strategy. Under the S-BC scenario, the service provision did not turn out to be profitable in any case. Due to the lack of an operation strategy, as soon as the battery is fully charged or discharged, it is no longer able to provide services, which results in high unavailability penalties. Under the POP strategy, the services provision results are always profitable. This fact lets us conclude that using suitable operation strategies increases the chance of obtaining revenues from participating in PFR markets. In general, in terms of the P^{bid} , regardless of the EV brand for Case A, the EV owners could

TABLE I
ANNUAL BENEFIT FOR CASE A: WITHOUT CONSIDERING CUSTOMER PREFERENCES [€/YEAR]

Pbid	CP				OF				POP			
	Outlander	iOn	N-Evalia	N-Leaf	Outlander	iOn	N-Evalia	N-Leaf	Outlander	iOn	N-Evalia	N-Leaf
1	204.05	204.05	204.05	204.05	204.05	204.05	204.05	204.05	204.05	204.05	204.05	204.05
2	408.10	408.10	408.10	408.10	408.10	408.10	408.10	408.10	408.10	408.10	408.10	408.10
3	-612.16	612.16	612.16	612.16	-612.16	612.16	612.16	612.16	612.16	612.16	612.16	612.16
4	-816.21	-816.21	816.21	816.21	-816.21	-816.21	816.21	816.21	816.21	816.21	816.21	816.21
5	-1020.26	-1020.26	-1020.26	1020.26	-1020.26	-1020.26	1020.26	1020.26	1020.26	1020.26	1020.26	1020.26
6	-1224.31	-1224.31	-1224.31	1224.31	-1224.31	-1224.31	-1224.31	1224.31	1224.31	1224.31	1224.31	1224.31
7	-1428.37	-1428.37	-1428.37	-1428.37	-1428.37	-1428.37	-1428.37	-1428.37	1428.37	1428.37	1428.37	1428.37
8	-1664.59	-1632.42	-1632.42	-1632.42	-1698.79	-1632.42	-1632.42	-1632.42	1632.42	1632.42	1632.42	1632.42
9	-2169.53	-1836.47	-1836.47	-1836.47	-2206.62	-1836.47	-1952.51	-1955.21	1836.47	1836.47	1836.47	1836.47
10	-2748.37	-2169.13	-2177.33	-2179.90	-2792.35	-2188.63	-2202.72	-2206.65	2040.52	2040.52	1920.13	1914.41

TABLE II
ANNUAL BENEFIT FOR CASE B: CONSIDERING CUSTOMER PREFERENCES [€/YEAR]

Pbid	CP				OF				POP			
	Outlander	iOn	N-Evalia	N-Leaf	Outlander	iOn	N-Evalia	N-Leaf	Outlander	iOn	N-Evalia	N-Leaf
1	110.53	110.53	110.53	110.53								
2	-221.05	221.05	221.05	221.05	-221.05	221.05	221.05	221.05	221.05	221.05	221.05	221.05
3	-331.59	-331.59	331.59	331.59	-331.59	-331.59	331.59	331.59	331.59	331.59	331.59	331.59
4	-442.11	-442.11	-442.11	442.11	-442.11	-442.11	-442.11	442.11	442.11	442.11	442.11	442.11
5	-552.64	-552.64	-552.64	-552.64	-552.64	-552.64	-552.64	-552.64	552.64	552.64	552.64	552.64
6	-663.17	-663.17	-663.17	-663.17	-663.17	-663.17	-663.17	-663.17	663.17	663.17	663.17	663.17
7	-773.70	-773.70	-773.70	-773.70	-773.70	-773.70	-773.70	-773.70	773.70	773.70	773.70	773.70
8	-884.23	-884.23	-884.23	-884.23	-884.23	-884.23	-884.23	-884.23	884.23	884.23	884.23	884.23
9	-994.75	-994.75	-994.75	-994.75	-994.75	-994.75	-994.75	-994.75	994.75	994.75	994.75	994.75
10	-1105.28	-1105.28	-1175.51	-1178.08	-1105.28	-1176.02	-1186.66	-1190.65	1105.28	1105.28	1105.28	1105.28

obtain benefits from providing FCR-N if the P^{bid} is up to 2kW, thereby producing annual benefits of around €400 per year (See Table I). For Case B, the EV owners can assure benefits by participating in the PFR market with a maximum 1kW, thus generating benefits of approximately €100 per year (Table II). The benefit is the same for all EVs because the incomes from providing FCR-N are calculated by using a capacity payment scheme based on the power bid. It means that the EV owners will receive a fixed amount of money regardless of the usage of P^{bid} , unless penalization costs (unavailability, grid impact, and battery degradation) appear. Results from Tables I and II also show that bidding the maximum capacity of the charger (i.e., 10 kW) is not always the best choice for all the EVs. For instance, in the OF strategy, the maximum bid is 2 kW for the outlander, 3 kW for the iOn, 5 kW for the N-Evalia, and 6 kW for the N-Leaf for Case A, while the POP strategy allows bidding the maximum capacity for all EVs while producing benefits for the owners. It demonstrates that the benefit can be higher, depending on the EV brand and the operation strategy used for the EV operation, which will be further discussed later.

Additionally, the results shown in Tables I and II are somehow comparable with the results from [19] and [22]. They may differ not only because of the considerations for the economic calculations in each approach but also because the costs associated with service unavailability, grid impact, and degradation are disregarded in those works. Table III shows a comparison in terms of the annual revenue and the optimal power bid for the EV Nissan Leaf, in which it is possible to observe that grid impact penalties and battery degradation do influence the annual benefits that an EV owner may obtain from providing FCR-N. It is reflected by the lower revenue obtained from the proposed method for comparable values of P^{bid} . However, Table II shows that the POP strategy allows bidding the maximum P^{bid} (i.e., 10 kW) and produce revenues equal to 1105.28 €/year while avoiding penalties for service

TABLE III
ECONOMIC COMPARISON WITH PREVIOUS LITERATURE OF FCR-N PROVISION BY THE EV NISSAN LEAF

Ref.	Power bid			Annual revenue (Approximated)			Considerations in [19] and [22]
	[22]	[19]	Proposed method*	[22]	[19]	Proposed method*	
Case B	9.25	10	10	1300.00	1395.00	1105.28	Without considering costs related to service unavailability, grid impact, and degradation

* Under the pop strategy

unavailability, grid impact, and already considering battery degradation costs. It is almost the same revenue reported in [19] for $P^{bid}=6.9$ kW, which probably would be much less if those costs would have been considered within the economic calculation, demonstrating the potential of the proposed method.

C. Impact of the operation strategies on the benefits

It is clear from Tables I and II that selecting a proper operation strategy can potentially increase the chance of obtaining more benefits. For instance, in Case A, when using the CP strategy, the EV N-Evalia can obtain benefits of around €800 by bidding into the market up to 4kW. However, using the OF strategy makes it possible for the same EV to increase the P^{bid} up to 5kW by producing benefits of around €1020. Similarly, for the EV N-Leaf, by using the CP and OF strategies the benefits are around €1220 with P^{bid} up to 6kW. Nonetheless, the POP strategy allows both the EVs N-Evalia and N-Leaf to bid more (up to the maximum capacity; i.e., 10kW) and still obtain benefits (€1900, approximately). Besides, the POP strategy provides more flexibility for all of the EVs and results in profits for any P^{bid} option. These results let us conclude that using operation strategies improves the participation of EVs in PFR markets. They help to increase the power bid and generate higher benefits for EV owners. It should be mentioned that results from the POP strategy always show profits because there were not penalization costs activated within this power bid range. However, larger power bids may provoke cycles with a larger depth of discharge (DoD), and a higher grid impact, since the time percentage of grid impact for P^{bid} equal to 10 kW is almost 5% (close to the allowed limit $\bar{\varphi}$ as shown in Fig. 3). Therefore, larger power bids may reduce the economic benefit, or even provokes unprofitable results.

Moreover, it is worth mentioning that the charger losses may decrease the calculate profit, as losses may increase the unavailability time. For instance, simulations showed that by considering a charging/discharging efficiency (η^c) equal to 90% applied to the Case B, the benefit for the EV N-Leaf under the POP strategy was reduced by approximately 7%, when offering the maximum P^{bid} . Nevertheless, EV users can still obtain benefits even if the charging efficiency is not unitary.

D. Impact of the costs on the benefit calculation

The income from providing FCR-N is calculated by using a capacity payment scheme. It means that, regardless of the EV brand or the battery capacity, the EV owner will always receive money for being available, and the income only depends on the P^{bid} . Then, the benefit could be primarily affected by the costs, which are more variable. Fig. 3 shows the corresponding parameters for

Fig. 3. Comparison between the strategies in terms of the parameters for Case B: a) Unavailability; b) Grid impact and c) Battery degradation.

each operation strategy for Case B, which aims to understand the composition of the objective function in terms of the costs. Fig. 3a) shows the unavailability time per year for each P^{bid} option. It can be seen from Fig. 3a) that under the CP and OF strategies there are some P^{bid} options in which the unavailability exceeds the permitted limit (i.e., 1%), thus reducing the benefits of certain EVs. Differently, under the POP strategy the unavailability time was less than 1% for all of the EVs and all the P^{bid} options. By analyzing the grid impact parameter, in Fig. 3b) it can be seen that the penalties for the grid impact starts to appear when P^{bid} is greater than 6kW for all of the strategies. It is expected as a result of the maximum power consumption allowed, which is defined as 7kW. Moreover, it reflects the fact that, during some periods, the system faces under-frequencies so that the maximum P^{bid} is required. It causes EVs to occasionally provoke congestion problems during periods that are higher than the allowed amount (i.e., 5%). Note that under the POP strategy, this limit is always maintained by all of the EVs. Additionally, Fig. 3c) shows that within the CP and OF strategies, EVs with less battery capacity (i.e., Outlander and iOn) have a degradation that is higher than 0.5% for

Fig. 4. Comparison between the parameters under the POP strategy: a) Case A and b) Case B.

the maximum P^{bid} . However, within the POP strategy, the degradation is less than 0.5% for all the EVs. It can be also observed that there is a direct relationship between P^{bid} and the degradation.

The unavailability time for any P^{bid} option was very high, regardless of the EV brand, under the S-CB scenario. This scenario provokes high penalization costs that result in a non-profitable service. Moreover, the grid impact and battery degradation parameters were almost zero for all of the P^{bid} options because the battery remains unavailable most of the time under this scenario.

This analysis shows that the unavailability and the grid impact parameters have a higher influence on the calculation of the benefit, even more than the battery degradation. Under the POP strategy, all of the parameters were maintained within the allowed limits, thus resulting in a benefit given only by the capacity payment. For this reason, the services provision always generates profitable results and the benefit is the same, regardless of the EV brand. However, for the other strategies, the benefit is more dependent on the chosen values for the parameters. If values that are more rigorous were considered, more robust solutions would be obtained, perhaps reducing the benefit. On the contrary, if the chosen parameters are more flexible, then the benefit could increase. A sensitivity analysis will be carried out afterward to verify this remark.

E. Impact of the customer preferences on the benefits

Comparing the results for Case A and B, it is possible to see from Tables I and II that reducing the usable capacity of the EV and considering its daily operation affects the maximum P^{bid} . Consequently, a significant reduction in the benefit is reflected. For

Fig. 5. Variation of the benefit to \bar{T} under the OF strategy.

Fig. 6. Variation of the benefit to $\bar{\varphi}$ under the POP strategy.

instance, analyzing the EV N-Evalia under the OF strategy in Case B, the P^{bid} and the benefits are reduced by approximately 67% when compared to Case A. Similarly, for the EV N-Leaf, the reduction for both variables is around 64%. However, even when reducing the usable capacity and when considering the EV daily operation, the EV owner can still obtain benefits from providing services, bidding up to 3 kW for the case of the EV N-Evalia, or up to 4 kW for the case of the EV N-Leaf. Additionally, it was found that under the POP strategy the service provision was profitable, regardless of the consideration of the customer preferences.

When comparing the parameters that compose the costs for both Cases, it is possible to see from Fig. 4, that for both cases and for all of the EVs, the unavailability time and the degradation were always maintained within the limits (represented by the dashed red lines). On the contrary, a particular finding was observed for the EVs N-Evalia and N-Leaf in Case A, which exceeded the grid impact limitation as can be seen in Fig. 4a. This occurred because a higher battery capacity results in an increased possibility to provide more power when required. Thus, this event is less likely for EVs with less battery capacity, such as the Outlander and iOn.

F. Sensitivity analysis for the maximum unavailability time, maximum grid impact time and battery degradation

As previously mentioned in Section IV-E, the costs (which are given by the chosen parameters for the maximum unavailability time (\bar{T}), maximum grid impact time ($\bar{\varphi}$) and battery degradation) have a strong influence on the benefit calculation. Thus, a

sensitivity analysis was carried out to determine the variation of the benefit when adjusting these parameters for the EV N-Leaf in Case B. Figure 5 shows the maximum benefit obtained under the OF strategy after the \bar{T} variation. Note in Fig. 5 that when \bar{T} increased, the maximum P^{bid} and the benefit also increased, which shows that the benefit is very sensitive to this parameter under this strategy. A similar analysis was carried out under the POP strategy, for which it was found that this parameter does not provoke strong changes in the benefit calculation. The benefit is the same for all $\bar{T} > 1\%$, unless a perfect performance of the service was required (i.e., $\bar{T} = 0\%$), which may be an unlikely result in real applications. These outcomes are aligned with the fact that, within this strategy, the unavailability time is very small (e.g., it is always less than 0.65% for the EV N-Leaf). A similar behavior was observed for the other EVs.

On the other hand, the variation of $\bar{\varphi}$ under the OF strategy does not improve the benefit in any case. The maximum P^{bid} remained equal to 4kW as in the main results; on the contrary, if $\bar{\varphi}$ is reduced, then the services provision remains unprofitable for power bids greater than 4kW and it gets worse for power bids greater than 7kW. When analyzing the results under the POP strategy, slight changes in the benefit were observed. Since the POP strategy resulted profitably in all cases, the benefit may only be reduced until 5% when reducing $\bar{\varphi}$ (See Fig. 6). Similar results were observed for the other EVs. Additionally, it is worth mentioning that if the maximum power consumption were disregarded, then the benefit would increase for all of the EVs.

When analyzing the battery degradation cost influence on the benefit, it was found that battery degradation might decrease the benefit, especially for the EVs with less capacity. If a small number of cycles are considered, then the benefit is reduced for the EV Outlander and iOn when compared with the maximum benefit that was initially calculated. This fact is also reflected in the maximum P^{bid} ; for instance, if less than 1000 cycles are considered in the case of the EV Outlander, then the power bid should be reduced to less than 7kW to maximize the benefit. After a determined number of cycles, the benefit converges to the same value for all of the EVs; thus, all of the EVs could participate in the market by bidding their maximum capacity (i.e., 10 kW).

V. DISCUSSION

V2G technology plays an important role in the electrification of the transportation sector since it provides flexibility services by EVs. This is still an on-developing technology that, like any emerging technology has barriers for practical implementations related to political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legislative factors [56]. However, there is notable interest in adopting this technology in the future EV market demonstrated by various on-going and finished R&D projects regarding V2G [11]. It is worth mentioning that, the V2G mode has been considered for the FCR-N application studied in this paper since the chargers used in the Parker Project are all Enel V2G chargers [57]. However, in case of the absence of this technology, frequency regulation, FCR-N, and other services could be provided using unidirectional chargers, but at the expense of significantly reducing the economic benefits for EV owners [26].

On the other hand, it should be mentioned that the proposed method can be extended to provide secondary reserve (and also primary reserve in other markets) by simply adapting or modifying the droop-control that governs each service. However, some investigations have claimed that providing secondary reserve via EVs is not as economic as primary reserve for various reasons, e.g., the reaction time needed is slower, the duration of full availability is longer, the procurement period is longer (e.g., yearly or monthly) [12], [58]. Hence, secondary reserves may not be as profitable as primary reserves. This situation may be different from country to country, having into account that regulation markets change drastically according to each market and transmission system operator (TSO).

VI. CONCLUSION

This work presented an assessment of the economic benefit for electric vehicle (EV) owners participating in the primary frequency regulation (PFR) market. A heuristic method was proposed to optimize the power bid that maximizes the EV owners' revenue along with a set of operational strategies that facilitates the service provision. The simulation results demonstrated that EV owners can obtain significant benefits by providing frequency-controlled normal operation reserves (FCR-N) in the Nord Pool market.

It was found that costs associated with the unavailability of service and the grid impact have a strong influence on the benefit, even more than the battery degradation. For instance, results showed that EVs with less battery capacity present a high risk of unavailability fines or battery degradation costs when bidding high power bids (it is because the battery might be fully charged or discharged quickly). However, results also demonstrated that the usage of operation strategies helps to reduce or even avoid those costs. Therefore, selecting a proper operational strategy can potentially increase profits by decreasing the unavailability of service as well as battery degradation.

Three operation strategies were analyzed: complete pause, over-fulfillment, and the preferred operating point (POP) mechanism. The comparison analysis among the three strategies proved that more sophisticated strategies such as POP, allows offering higher power bids and increasing the chance of obtaining more benefits. It was demonstrated that even by bidding into the market with a low power capacity of 1 kW, EV owners are able to obtain an annual benefit of around €100. This 1 kW bid results in a profit for all operation strategies and avoids the risk of incurring fines because of service unavailability or grid impact. The application of POP was the best operation strategy, decreasing both the unavailability period and battery degradation. Under the POP strategy, EV owners are able to bid with the nominal capacity of the charger, which was 10 kW, and obtain a yearly profit of up to €1100. This yearly profit can be achieved regardless of the EV battery capacity.

Results also showed that considering the daily operation of EVs (i.e., customer preferences) significantly reduces the benefit that the EV owner may obtain (around 58% less), which demonstrates that the users' preferences play an important role within the

economic calculations. In addition, results from the sensitivity analysis showed that the variations of the benefit highly depend on the operation strategy under analysis. The POP strategy proved to be less sensitive to variations of the maximum unavailability time and grid impact time, while the others showed significant variations of the benefit.

As a final remark, given the flexibility of the proposed method, it could be adapted to validate its performance in other primary frequency regulation markets, e.g., the Pennsylvania-New Jersey-Maryland (PJM) market in California, as part of future works. Furthermore, considering that the proposed method allows the assessment of the economic benefits of EVs participating in PFR markets from the EV owner perspective, it is worth adopting and validating the proposed method and operation strategies to maximize the revenue from the aggregator perspective.

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